

A systematic review of the linkages between corporate governance systems and procurement practices in public procurement entities

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Abstract

Purpose – Corporate governance and procurement corruption has long been recognized as a social problem, but the subject has received scant academic attention in prevailing literature on the management of procurement in Ghana. A systematic review conducted explores how the relationship between corporate governance and procurement could contribute to the effective management of public resources to maximize social welfare and augment Ghana's economy.

Design/methodology/approach – Drawing extensively on existing literature as a secondary data source, this research adopts an interpretivist philosophical stance and inductive reasoning to explore corporate governance and procurement corruption. The approach underpinning this overarching epistemology, adopts a three-step sample selection strategy to identify the range and scope of publications on the phenomena under investigation. Scientific papers were searched manually from Scopus and carefully screened for analysis.

Findings – Analysis suggests that corporate governance and procurement require a degree of coordinated change across governmental departments, such as planning, legal and procurement to implement a robust policy and related support systems. Furthermore, it was observed that a portfolio approach to inter-organizational collaboration with different partners (such as the Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) as well as State Owned Enterprises and Corporations) was not coordinated sufficiently to effectively generate public interest. Albeit each partner has individual own objectives, they ultimately complement one another. A portfolio of different, inter-organizational arrangements enables several complementary instruments and various logics to be used in achieving overall organisational goals and objectives.

Originality/value – Novel insight presented provides an invaluable opportunity to: further expand future research into corporate governance and procurement in Ghana; and consequently, provide the premise upon which to build meaningful empirical analysis such as comparing the extent of corruption practices in various sectors of the Ghanaian economy.

Key words: Corporate governance; Procurement management; Public procurement; Public procurement entities; Corporate governance

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1. Introduction

Accountability in public procurement remains one of the most challenging issues in developing countries (Brinkerhoff and Brinkerhoff, 2015). Government institutions' accountability in oversight functions for managing public resources is weak because many developing countries do not have a public procurement system based on open competition, transparency and market principles (Kajimbwa, 2018). In Ghana, accountability and transparency in public procurement became a concern to prominent stakeholders (such as Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) and State Owned Enterprises and Corporations) and this led to the enactment of the Public Procurement Authority that is mandated to ensure that all procurement entities achieve value for money for Ghanaian citizens PPA Act 2003, (Act 663) as amended.

Governance is a contentious term to define (cf. Henry and Tysiachniouk, 2018) because different institutions define it to fit the realisation of their objectives (Carlisle and Gruby, 2019). The World Bank (WB) has defined governance as: *"the existence of political power to manage a nation's affairs"* (Engel *et al.*, 2017). Whereas the European Union (EU) Commission has defined governance as: *"the principles and tools for decision-making within the context of multiple layers and decision-makers"* (Saurugger and Terpan, 2021). From the two definitions, one may conclude that the WB's governance definition is applicable at the national level whilst, the EU Commission's definition is the operationalized definition that describes the decision-making process in government at different levels/layers of decision making. Put simply, any decision made at any level of government must follow defined steps, processes and/or principles using appropriate tools. Within the UK, the Department for International Development defines *'good governance'* as: *"how institutions, rules and systems of the state- executive, legislature, judiciary and military-operate at the central and local level and how the state relates to individual citizens, civil society and the private sector"* (Parthasarathy, 2019). This definition indisputably means that whatever happens (at whatever level of the branch of government), the process should be performed based on rules and systems that has an interest of the populace, civil society and private sector.

Effective procurement practices provide government with a means of bringing about social, environmental and economic reforms (Velenturf *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, a procurement decision made by the government at whatever level should be made with a focus on improving the well-being of citizens as well as ensuring that the private sector benefits from it (Lam and Yang, 2020). However, the procurement process should stand the scrutiny of civil society to ensure that public procurement decisions are based on set principles namely accountability, transparency, fairness and ethics (Fourie, 2017). It is from these principles and the fact that public procurement decisions affect citizens, that the civil society and the private sectors are the major pillars of holding various governments responsible for meeting citizens' needs (Mensah, 2019). In other words, public procurement is a governance issue (Saussier and Valbonesi, 2018) that aims at maximising social welfare and value for the majority of the populace. Accountability is critical in public procurement because the person making a procurement decision is doing so on behalf of the populace. Moreover, government procurement involves the spending of huge sums of public resources which can tempt government officials to enrich themselves through awarding of contracts to their clienteles, sympathisers or themselves (Rose-Ackerman and Palifka, 2016). Consequently, accountability in procurement can be ensured through the implementation of legislation that hold those participating in public procurement accountable for their decisions, ensuring that the general public benefits from any procurement, swiftly and effectively.

Procurement and supply chain management are also governance issues because of political and managerial will for these activities to achieve their primary objectives of value for money and benefiting the ultimate user of the goods, works and services (Adjei-Bamfo and Maloreh-Nyamekye, 2019). According to WB's definition for governance, there should be a political power in managing national affairs which could also reside at a lower level (i.e., at the local government level) or delegated to other levels (Mabveka, 2004). Therefore, the political leadership should enact laws that would establish appropriate institutions, rules and systems to regulate and monitor public procurement and supply management (Olatunji *et al.*, 2016). Political influence is effective when political leadership is also willing to adhere to the enacted laws to demonstrate that it is practicing good governance (Rothstein and Teorell, 2008). The enactment of laws is a separate issue from their observance and/or enforcement while managing national affairs, which includes the acquisition of products, works and services (Cohen *et al.*, 2016). The judiciary should be able to provide remedy to persons who have been harmed by the refusal of any ministry, department or institution of government under any branch of government to follow the laws that have been enacted (Asare and Prempeh, 2016).

Every government expenditure requires public procurement since it is the sole vehicle that promotes discipline, openness, fairness and equity, resulting in value for money (Chigudu 2014). Public procurement is a method that triangulates unethical purchase in the public sector, where discrepancies and violations are common (Reilley *et al.*, 2020). The temptation and potential for unethical procurement activities exist with every Cedi (Ghana's currency) that

comes through government procurement. Unethical procurement is said to have taken place, if the stakeholders involved (either intentionally or unintentionally) undertook a procurement activity that is inconsistent with the laid down rules, regulations and procedures and has the tendency of compromising the achievement of value for money (VfM) (World Bank, 2012). Unethical public procurement practices prohibit the public sector from obtaining goods or services at the lowest possible tariff (Mazibuko and Fourie, 2017). Procurement blunders that stifle competition throughout the planning or budgeting stages may be deemed unethical procurement practices (Sian and Smyth, 2021). In Ghana, the Public Procurement Act 2003, (Act 663) as amended and the Public Financial Management Act 2016, (Act 921) have given prominence to the objectives of value for money, integrity in public spending practices, accountability to the public and efficiency as the primary drivers for procurement and unethical procurement practices should be controlled.

Considering the importance that the Ghanaian public place upon how their taxes are spent, there has been increasing calls for accountability from central governments (Standing and Hilson, 2013). This has prompted interested parties such as the World Bank, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), the African Development Bank (AfDB), and others to increase resources to African governments to improve the efficiency and efficacy of government spending. Despite the interventions made in achieving this, scant research has investigated corporate governance and public procurement in Ghana; where the former is essential as constitutes a universal set for the latter. In view of this, the two variables are assumed to be the same by other stakeholders and this may affect public procurement effectiveness. Hence, there is a need for an empirical review on the various contributions made in the areas of corporate governance and procurement and to suggest the ways and means of strengthening the two variables for the purpose of maximising social welfare in the public sector.

Against this contextual backdrop, this current study seeks to establish what research has been carried out within the area of procurement and supply chain management of the public entities in Ghana. Concomitant objectives are to: investigate the contribution of scholarly research on strengthening corporate governance in Ghana; establish the relationship between corporate governance and public procurement; and generate polemic debate by providing recommendations that guide future academic works.

2. Research method

Source: Adapted from Wu *et al.* (2019)

Figure 1 Sample systematic literature review selection procedure

This research adopts an interpretivist philosophical stance and inductive reasoning (cf. Burton *et al.*, 2021; Bayramova *et al.*, 2021; Posillico *et al.*, 2021) to explore corporate governance and procurement corruption. This epistemological positioning has been widely used for similar review studies conducted. For example, Chamberlain *et al.*, (2019) studied mega event orchestration using bibliometrics; Newman *et al.*, (2020) conducted a literature review of Industry 4.0

deployment in the construction industry; and Edwards *et al.*, (1998) reviewed predictive maintenance techniques and their relevance to construction plant. Therefore, this approach is deemed valid for the present study. With reference to approach, a comprehensive literature review is predicated on a systematic evaluation of prior publications in scientific peer reviewed journals (Tsai and Wen, 2005; Yi and Wang, 2013; Akinlolu *et al.*, 2020; Spellacy *et al.*, 2020). In this study, a three-step sample selection strategy is adopted to identify the range and scope of publications on the theme of public procurement and corporate governance. Specifically, this involves: 1) selecting the database; 2) searching for research papers; and 3) extracting the sample papers for the study (cf. Pärn *et al.*, 2017; Roberts *et al.*, 2018; Smith *et al.*, 2020; Ahmed *et al.*, 2021). Adapted from Wu *et al.* (2019), the procedure for selecting review sample papers is shown in Figure 1.

2.1. Selecting the database

In identifying pertinent peer-reviewed journal articles that are relevant to the subject matter, (i.e., corporate governance and public procurement), several established databases were considered, such as Scopus, PubMed, Web of Science, Google Scholar, Direct Open Access to Books (DOAB), Sage and Science Direct. A comparison of these engines determined that Scopus offered the most timely, up-to-date data and comprehensive (Wu *et al.*, 2019). Thus, Scopus is adopted as the search platform. It is recognized as competing favourably with the more traditional worldwide search engines with an extensive database and accompanying data analytics, now much favoured by researchers (Prasad *et al.*, 2019).

2.2. Searching for research papers

The key words were identified by first manually selecting five articles on the topic area to help determine the most prudent search terms. The resultant keywords used in the search were ‘corporate governance’ or ‘cg’, ‘procurement, procurement management’, ‘public procurement’, ‘public procurement entities’ and ‘public procurement’ and ‘corporate governance’. The search rule was: (TITLE-ABS-KEY (“corporate governance” OR “public procurement” OR “corporate governance practices” OR “procurement and organizational sustainability” OR “public entities” OR “goal of public procurement” AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2017) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, “ar”)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, “English”)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE, “j”))). Consequently, as evidenced in the literature search results, only a limited number of pertinent articles were identified. The search was conducted between 1st July 2021 to 10th July 2021 for papers published over the past five years. The search was limited to articles published in English and papers written from 2016 to date 2021; it is acknowledged that this may present a limitation of the work given that good science is also published in non-English speaking journals.

2.3. Extracting the sample papers for the study

Because the initial search results included all papers related to corporate governance (CG) and public procurement (PP), it was necessary to exclude studies that were not also related to procurement management or that were not born with corporate governance and public procurement practices. This was done through systematic and careful manual review of papers (as part of a data cleansing process) to extract those papers that were relevant. In the process, the titles and abstracts, as well as the content of the identified paper were assessed. Though time-consuming, the procedure was rigorous, and ultimately twenty-four (24) papers pertinent to corporate governance practices and public procurement were finally selected for the study – refer to Table 1. The next step required the categorization of the studies into specific underlying themes. Detailed content analyses of the classified themes followed, also setting out literature gaps and delineating future research direction.

Table 1 Selected Papers for the Review

S/N	Author(s)	Title of Paper
1	Patrucco, A.S., Luzzini, D. and Ronchi, S.	Research perspectives on public procurement: Content analysis of 14 years of publications in the journal of public procurement
2	Rendon, J.M. and Rendon, R.G.	Procurement fraud in the US Department of Defense: Implications for contracting processes and internal controls
3	Glas, A.H., Schaupp, M. and Essig, M.	An organizational perspective on the implementation of strategic goals in public procurement

4	Ibrahim, M., Bawole, J.N., Obuobisa-Darko, T., Abubakar, A.B. and Kumasey, A.S.	The legal regime and the compliance façade in public procurement in Ghana.
5	Asiedu, R.O. and Adaku, E.	Cost overruns of public sector construction projects: a developing country perspective
6	Ambaw, B.A. and Telgen, J	The practice of performance-based contracting in developing countries' public procurement: the case of Ethiopia
7	Mahamadu, A.M., Manu, P., Booth, C., Olomolaiye, P., Coker, A., Ibrahim, A. and Lamond, J.	Infrastructure procurement skills gap amongst procurement personnel in Nigeria's public sector
8	Rogerson, M., Crane, A., Soundararajan, V., Grosvold, J. and Cho, C.H.	Organisational responses to mandatory modern slavery disclosure legislation: a failure of experimentalist governance
9	Ghansah, F.A., Owusu-Manu, D.G., Ayarkwa, J., Edwards, D.J. and Hosseini, M.R.	Assessing the level of awareness of smart building technologies (SBTs) in the developing countries
10	Kivisto, T. and Virolainen, V.M.	Public procurement spend analysis at a national level in Finland
11	Di Mauro, C., Ancarani, A. and Hartley, T.	Unravelling SMEs' participation and success in public procurement
12	Ottou, J.A., Baiden, B.K. and Nani, G.	Six Sigma Project Procurement application in public procurement
13	Talebi, A. and Rezanian, D.	Governance of projects in public procurement of innovation a multi-level perspective
14	Kajimbwa, M.G.A.	Benchmarking accountability of local government authorities in public procurement in Tanzania
15	Lampsey, T., Owusu-Manu, D.G., Acheampong, A., Adesi, M. and Ghansah, F.A.	A framework for the adoption of green business models in the Ghanaian construction industry
16	Alferaih, A.	Understanding causal links among the dimensions of corporate social responsibility: a framework developed using interpretive structural modelling
17	Ahmed, H., Edwards, D.J., Lai, J.H., Roberts, C., Debrah, C., Owusu-Manu, D.G. and Thwala, W.D.	Post occupancy evaluation of school refurbishment projects: Multiple case study in the UK. <i>Buildings</i>
18	Changalima, I.A., Mushi, G.O. and Mwiseje, S.S.	Procurement planning as a strategic tool for public procurement effectiveness: Experience from selected public procuring entities in Dodoma city, Tanzania
19	Hakansson, H. and Axelsson, B	What is so special with outsourcing in the public sector
20	Knebel, S. and Seele, P.	Introducing public procurement tenders as part of corporate communications: A typological analysis based on CSR reporting indicators
21	Owusu-Manu, D.G., Kukah, A.S., Boateng, F., Asumadu, G. and Edwards, D.J.	Exploring strategies to reduce moral hazard and adverse selection of Ghanaian public-private partnership (PPP) construction projects
22	Ameyaw, C., Abaitey, B.A., Mensah, S. and Manu, E.	Assessing the cost of competitive tendering in Ghana using transaction cost theory
23	Manu, P., Asiedu, R.O., Mahamadu, A.M., Olomolaiye, P.O., Booth, C., Manu, E., Ajayi, S. and Agyekum, K.	Contribution of procurement capacity of public agencies to attainment of procurement objectives in infrastructure procurement
24	Kissi, E., Agyekum, K., Musah, L., Owusu-Manu, D.G. and Debrah, C.	Linking supply chain disruptions with organisational performance of construction firms: the moderating role of innovation

3. Citation-based analysis

The journal publishing outlets were also assessed by identifying journals that published papers on corporate governance practices and public procurement.

3.1. Studies on Corporate Governance Practices

Table 2 presents the articles, ranked in descending order of citations received, also showing author(s), years of publication, as well as the article title. Results identify that the most two cited articles were: Rendon, J.M. and Rendon, R.G. with 63 citations for their publication in *Managerial Auditing Journal* titled: “Procurement fraud in the US Department of Defense: Implications for contracting processes and internal controls,” published in 2016; and Patrucco, A.S., Luzzini, D. and Ronchi, S. with 66 citations for their publications entitled: “Research perspectives on public procurement: Content analysis of 5 years of publications in the journal of public procurement”, *Journal of Public Procurement* published in 2017. Another paper highly cited paper was authored by Glas, A.H., Schaupp, M. and Essig, M. with 34 citations for their publication entitled “An organizational perspective on the implementation of strategic goals in public procurement” *Journal of Public Procurement*, published in 2017. The remaining 21 papers were all referred journal papers. Three publications have yet to receive citations, possibly because they have only been in the public domain for a couple of years. These include ‘Assessing the cost of competitive tendering in Ghana using transaction cost theory’ and ‘Exploring strategies to reduce moral hazard and adverse selection of Ghanaian public-private partnership (PPP) construction projects’ by Ameyaw *et al.*, (2021) and Manu *et al.*, (2021) respectively.

Table 2 Selected Papers for the Review (Citations)

S/N	Author(s)	Title of Paper	No. of Citations
1	Patrucco, A.S., Luzzini, D. and Ronchi, S	Research perspectives on public procurement: Content analysis of 14 years of publications in the journal of public procurement	66
2	Rendon, J.M. and Rendon, R.G.	Procurement fraud in the US Department of Defense: Implications for contracting processes and internal controls	63
3	Glas, A.H., Schaupp, M. and Essig, M.	An organizational perspective on the implementation of strategic goals in public procurement	34
4	Ibrahim, M., Bawole, J.N., Obuobisa-Darko, T., Abubakar, A.B. and Kumasey, A.S.	The legal regime and the compliance façade in public procurement in Ghana.	18
5	Asiedu, R.O. and Adaku, E.	Cost overruns of public sector construction projects: a developing country perspective	12
6	Ambaw, B.A. and Telgen, J.	The practice of performance-based contracting in developing countries' public procurement: the case of Ethiopia	11
7	Mahamadu, A.M., Manu, P., Booth, C., Olomolaiye, P., Coker, A., Ibrahim, A. and Lamond, J.	Infrastructure procurement skills gap amongst procurement personnel in Nigeria's public sector	6
8	Rogerson, M., Crane, A., Soundararajan, V., Grosvold, J. and Cho, C.H.	Organisational responses to mandatory modern slavery disclosure legislation: a failure of experimentalist governance	4
9	Ghansah, F.A., Owusu-Manu, D.G., Ayarkwa, J., Edwards, D.J. and Hosseini, M.R.	Assessing the level of awareness of smart building technologies (SBTs) in the developing countries	4
10	Kivisto, T. and Virolainen, V.M.	Public procurement spend analysis at a national level in Finland	4

11	Di Mauro, C., Ancarani, A. and Hartley, T.	Unravelling SMEs' participation and success in public procurement	3
12	Ottou, J.A., Baiden, B.K. and Nani, G.	Six Sigma Project Procurement application in public procurement	3
13	Talebi, A. and Rezania, D.	Governance of projects in public procurement of innovation a multi-level perspective	3
14	Kajimbwa, M.G.A.	Benchmarking accountability of local government authorities in public procurement in Tanzania	3
15	Lamptey, T., Owusu-Manu, D.G., Acheampong, A., Adesi, M. and Ghansah, F.A.	A framework for the adoption of green business models in the Ghanaian construction industry	2
16	Alferaih, A.	Understanding causal links among the dimensions of corporate social responsibility: a framework developed using interpretive structural modelling	2
17	Ahmed, H., Edwards, D.J., Lai, J.H., Roberts, C., Debrah, C., Owusu-Manu, D.G. and Thwala, W.D.	Post occupancy evaluation of school refurbishment projects: Multiple case study in the UK.	1
18	Changalima, I.A., Mushi, G.O. and Mwiseje, S.S.	Procurement planning as a strategic tool for public procurement effectiveness: Experience from selected public procuring entities in Dodoma city, Tanzania	1
19	Hakansson, H. and Axelsson, B.	What is so special with outsourcing in the public sector	1
20	Knebel, S. and Seele, P.	Introducing public procurement tenders as part of corporate communications: A typological analysis based on CSR reporting indicators	1
21	Owusu-Manu, D.G., Kukah, A.S., Boateng, F., Asumadu, G. and Edwards, D.J.	Exploring strategies to reduce moral hazard and adverse selection of Ghanaian public-private partnership (PPP) construction projects	1
22	Ameyaw, C., Abaitey, B.A., Mensah, S. and Manu, E.	Assessing the cost of competitive tendering in Ghana using transaction cost theory	0
23	Manu, P., Asiedu, R.O., Mahamadu, A.M., Olomolaiye, P.O., Booth, C., Manu, E., Ajayi, S. and Agyekum, K.	Contribution of procurement capacity of public agencies to attainment of procurement objectives in infrastructure procurement	0
24	Kissi, E., Agyekum, K., Musah, L., Owusu-Manu, D.G. and Debrah, C.	Linking supply chain disruptions with organisational performance of construction firms: the moderating role of innovation	0

3.2. Journal Analysis

Journal analysis aims to identify the journals that have been used and referenced most frequently. Table 3 presents the list of journals that have published cited articles on corporate practices and procurement, shown in descending order of citations per paper published. As can be seen, the International Journal of *Public Procurement* has received the highest citations per paper (66 citations), followed by the *Managerial Auditing Journal* and Performance Management and the *Journal of Public Procurement*, with 63 and 34 citations respectively. There is no journal in the list which has received more than 70 citations, on average. The number of papers per journal is remarkably low, with each journal having only published a single article. Thus, while the number of published papers is also low, at 24, there is no journal that can be identified as the natural home for articles related to this theme. It is therefore, also highly likely that potential articles on corporate practices and procurement in construction have been rejected precisely because editors did not see their content as synergetic with their journals core themes or papers in the area were not of a suitable scientific quality to warrant publication (refer to Table 3). Consequently, researchers are widening their scope of search and relying on a pool of journals instead of being able to focus on few specialized journals.

Table 3 Journals of Publications (Specific journals of publications)

S/N	Author(s)	Title of Paper	Journal of Publication
1	Patrucco, A.S., Luzzini, D. and Ronchi, S.	Research perspectives on public procurement: Content analysis of 14 years of publications in the journal of public procurement	<i>Journal of Public Procurement</i>
2	Rendon, J.M. and Rendon, R.G.	Procurement fraud in the US Department of Defense: Implications for contracting processes and internal controls	<i>Managerial Auditing Journal</i>
3	Glas, A.H., Schaupp, M. and Essig, M.	An organizational perspective on the implementation of strategic goals in public procurement	<i>Journal of public procurement</i>
4	Ibrahim, M., Bawole, J.N., Obuobisa-Darko, T., Abubakar, A.B. and Kumasey, A.S.	The legal regime and the compliance façade in public procurement in Ghana.	<i>International Journal of Public Sector Management</i>
5	Asiedu, R.O. and Adaku, E.	Cost overruns of public sector construction projects: a developing country perspective	<i>International Journal of Managing Projects in Business</i>
6	Ambaw, B.A. and Telgen, J.	The practice of performance-based contracting in developing countries' public procurement: the case of Ethiopia	<i>Journal of public procurement</i>
7	Mahamadu, A.M., Manu, P., Booth, C., Olomolaiye, P., Coker, A., Ibrahim, A. and Lamond, J.	Infrastructure procurement skills gap amongst procurement personnel in Nigeria's public sector	<i>Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology</i>
8	Rogerson, M., Crane, A., Soundararajan, V., Grosvold, J. and Cho, C.H.	Organisational responses to mandatory modern slavery disclosure legislation: a failure of experimentalist governance	<i>Accounting, Auditing & Accountability</i>
9	Ghansah, F.A., Owusu-Manu, D.G., Ayarkwa, J., Edwards, D.J. and Hosseini, M.R.	Assessing the level of awareness of smart building technologies (SBTs) in the developing countries	<i>Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology</i>
10	Kivisto, T. and Virolainen, V.M.	Public procurement spend analysis at a national level in Finland	<i>Journal of Public Procurement</i>
11	Di Mauro, C., Ancarani, A. and Hartley, T.	Unravelling SMEs' participation and success in public procurement	<i>Journal of Public Procurement</i>
12	Ottou, J.A., Baiden, B.K. and Nani, G.	Six Sigma Project Procurement application in public procurement	<i>International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management</i>
13	Talebi, A. and Rezania, D.	Governance of projects in public procurement of innovation a multi-level perspective	<i>Journal of Public Procurement</i>
14	Kajimbwa, M.G.A.	Benchmarking accountability of local government authorities in public procurement in Tanzania	<i>Journal of Public Procurement</i>
15	Lamptey, T., Owusu-Manu, D.G., Acheampong, A., Adesi, M. and Ghansah, F.A.	A framework for the adoption of green business models in the Ghanaian construction industry	<i>Smart and Sustainable Built Environment</i>
16	Alferaih, A.	Understanding causal links among the dimensions of corporate social responsibility:	<i>Social Responsibility Journal.</i>

		a framework developed using interpretive structural modelling	
17	Ahmed, H., Edwards, D.J., Lai, J.H., Roberts, C., Debrah, C., Owusu-Manu, D.G. and Thwala, W.D.	Post occupancy evaluation of school refurbishment projects: Multiple case study in the UK. <i>Buildings</i>	<i>Smart and Sustainable Built Environment</i>
18	Changalima, I.A., Mushi, G.O. and Mwiseje, S.S.	Procurement planning as a strategic tool for public procurement effectiveness: Experience from selected public procuring entities in Dodoma city, Tanzania	<i>Journal of Public Procurement</i>
19	Hakansson, H. and Axelsson, B.	What is so special with outsourcing in the public sector	<i>Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing</i>
20	Knebel, S. and Seele, P.	Introducing public procurement tenders as part of corporate communications: A typological analysis based on CSR reporting indicators	<i>Corporate Communications: An International Journal</i>
21	Owusu-Manu, D.G., Kukah, A.S., Boateng, F., Asumadu, G. and Edwards, D.J.	Exploring strategies to reduce moral hazard and adverse selection of Ghanaian public-private partnership (PPP) construction projects	<i>Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology</i>
22	Ameyaw, C., Abaitey, B.A., Mensah, S. and Manu, E.	Assessing the cost of competitive tendering in Ghana using transaction cost theory	<i>Built Environment Project and Asset Management</i>
23	Manu, P., Asiedu, R.O., Mahamadu, A.M., Olomolaiye, P.O., Booth, C., Manu, E., Ajayi, S. and Agyekum, K.	Contribution of procurement capacity of public agencies to attainment of procurement objectives in infrastructure procurement	<i>Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management</i>
24	Kissi, E., Agyekum, K., Musah, L., Owusu-Manu, D.G. and Debrah, C.	Linking supply chain disruptions with organisational performance of construction firms: the moderating role of innovation	<i>Journal of Financial Management of Property and Construction</i>

Table 3 depicts the various journals as well as 24 keys publications within these. The frequency of publish articles within these journals are presented in Figure 2 below.

The journal that has the highest number of publications was 'Journal of Public Procurement' frequency (f) = 7 articles (or 29.17% of the sample). This was followed by the Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology with f = 3 (or 12.5%). The remaining journals had only one publication each. This analysis reveals that phenomena under review remains in an early development stage with very few papers actually linking corporate governance and public procurement.

Figure 2 Journals and the number of publications

3.3. Thematic breakup of the reviewed papers

Details of the emergent thematic areas derived from the data set are detailed in Table 3 and illustrates that the highest number of publications on the papers reviewed were on public procurement ($f = 10$ or 42%). This was followed by publications on corporate governance ($f = 6$ or 25%) of the total papers reviewed. The least number of published articles was on public procurement and corporate governance ($f = 1$ or 4%) of the total papers reviewed. Based on these results, it is apparent that research into the linkages between public procurement and corporate governance remains scant. Hence, there is the need for industry players and the academia to pay keen interest in the areas since a significant proportion of national budgets are spent on procurement and related activities.

4. Thematic analysis of the year of publications

4.1. Year of Publication Analysis

It is logical to assume that more contemporary research predominantly seeks to address current challenges but may receive a lower number of citations – hence, the year of publication is an insightful indicator. As a result, the analysis of the year of publication is justified. Table 4 shows the detailed year of publication for the various papers under consideration. In view of this the latest the year of public the more likely the paper addresses current problems or issues and the other way is true.

Table 5 presents a detailed breakdown of the various years of publications in percentage terms; where the years are arranged in descending order. The results presented indicate that the highest publication in a year was 2020 ($f = 10$ publications or 42% of the total publications). This was followed by 2021 and 2017 each with a $f = 4$ publications or 17% of the total publications. These results showed that most of the papers reviewed were current and the possibility addressing contemporary issues was detected. For example, Patrucco *et al.*, (2021) looked at perspectives on public procurement: content analysis of 14 years of publications in the journal of public procurement as one of the journals that received second highest citations. Again, Ghansah *et al.*, (2021) reviewed on assessing the level of awareness of

smart building technologies (SBTs) in the developing countries. These equally received the second highest citations as a result of the review area.

Table 4 Thematic grouping of reviewed papers

Serial Number (1)	Theme (2)	Number of Articles (3)	Percentage of Total Papers (4)
1	Public Procurement (PP)	10	42%
2	Corporate Governance (CG)	6	25%
3	Procurement Legal Framework (PLFW)	2	8%
4	Sustainable Procurement (SP)	3	13%
5	Procurement and Decentralization (PD)	2	8%
6	Procurement and Corporate Governance (PCG)	1	4%
	Total	24	100

Table 5 Year of Publications

S/N	Author(s)	Title of Paper	Year of Publication
1	Patrucco, A.S., Luzzini, D. and Ronchi, S.	Research perspectives on public procurement: Content analysis of 14 years of publications in the journal of public procurement	2017
2	Rendon, J.M. and Rendon, R.G.	Procurement fraud in the US Department of Defense: Implications for contracting processes and internal controls	2016
3	Glas, A.H., Schaupp, M. and Essig, M.	An organizational perspective on the implementation of strategic goals in public procurement	2017
4	Ibrahim, M., Bawole, J.N., Obuobisa-Darko, T., Abubakar, A.B. and Kumasey, A.S.	The legal regime and the compliance façade in public procurement in Ghana.	2017
5	Asiedu, R.O. and Adaku, E.	Cost overruns of public sector construction projects: a developing country perspective	2019
6	Ambaw, B.A. and Telgen, J.	The practice of performance-based contracting in developing countries' public procurement: the case of Ethiopia	2017
7	Mahamadu, A.M., Manu, P., Booth, C., Olomolaiye, P., Coker, A., Ibrahim, A. and Lamond, J.	Infrastructure procurement skills gap amongst procurement personnel in Nigeria's public sector	2018
8	Rogerson, M., Crane, A., Soundararajan, V., Grosvold, J. and Cho, C.H.	Organisational responses to mandatory modern slavery disclosure legislation: a failure of experimentalist governance	2020
9	Ghansah, F.A., Owusu-Manu, D.G., Ayarkwa, J., Edwards, D.J. and Hosseini, M.R.	Assessing the level of awareness of smart building technologies (SBTs) in the developing countries	2021

10	Kivisto, T. and Virolainen, V.M.	Public procurement spend analysis at a national level in Finland	2019
11	Di Mauro, C., Ancarani, A. and Hartley, T.	Unravelling SMEs' participation and success in public procurement	2020
12	Ottou, J.A., Baiden, B.K. and Nani, G.	Six Sigma Project Procurement application in public procurement	2020
13	Talebi, A. and Rezanian, D.	Governance of projects in public procurement of innovation a multi-level perspective	2020
14	Kajimbwa, M.G.A.	Benchmarking accountability of local government authorities in public procurement in Tanzania	2018
15	Lamprey, T., Owusu-Manu, D.G., Acheampong, A., Adesi, M. and Ghansah, F.A.	A framework for the adoption of green business models in the Ghanaian construction industry	2020
16	Alferaih, A.	Understanding causal links among the dimensions of corporate social responsibility: a framework developed using interpretive structural modelling	2019
17	Ahmed, H., Edwards, D.J., Lai, J.H., Roberts, C., Debrah, C., Owusu-Manu, D.G. and Thwala, W.D.	. Post occupancy evaluation of school refurbishment projects: Multiple case study in the UK.	2021
18	Changalima, I.A., Mushi, G.O. and Mwiseje, S.S.	Procurement planning as a strategic tool for public procurement effectiveness: Experience from selected public procuring entities in Dodoma city, Tanzania	2020
19	Hakansson, H. and Axelsson, B.	What is so special with outsourcing in the public sector	2020
20	Knebel, S. and Seele, P.	Introducing public procurement tenders as part of corporate communications: A typological analysis based on CSR reporting indicators	2020
21	Owusu-Manu, D.G., Kukah, A.S., Boateng, F., Asumadu, G. and Edwards, D.J.	Exploring strategies to reduce moral hazard and adverse selection of Ghanaian public-private partnership (PPP) construction projects	2020
22	Ameyaw, C., Abaitey, B.A., Mensah, S. and Manu, E.	Assessing the cost of competitive tendering in Ghana using transaction cost theory	2021
23	Manu, P., Asiedu, R.O., Mahamadu, A.M., Olomolaiye, P.O., Booth, C., Manu, E., Ajayi, S. and Agyekum, K.	Contribution of procurement capacity of public agencies to attainment of procurement objectives in infrastructure procurement	2021
24	Kissi, E., Agyekum, K., Musah, L., Owusu-Manu, D.G. and Debrah, C.	Linking supply chain disruptions with organisational performance of construction firms: the moderating role of innovation	2020

5. Corporate governance and procurement practices

Various research studies have been conducted on corporate governance and procurement (Mchunu, 2018). However, while some of these past studies have focused on different dimensions of corporate governance (Velte, 2017), others have been studied in different jurisdictions (Grosman, 2016). It is important to review these past studies to draw lessons and fill literature gaps. Osei-Tutu *et al.* (2010) explored and discussed corruption practices inherent in Ghanaian public procurement of infrastructural projects. Drawing extensively on existing literature and published data, the methodology adopted for the paper (*ibid*) consisted of multi-stage critical review of pertinent literature; a review of 2007 Annual Report of the Public Procurement Authority; and a review of the Public Procurement Act, 2003 (Act 663). The findings revealed that conflict of interest, bribery, embezzlement, kickbacks, tender manipulation and fraud are observed

corruption practices in the Ghanaian infrastructure projects delivery system. Osei-Tutu *et al.* (2010) revealed corruption in procurement for infrastructural projects but did not attach corporate governance practices in the overall focus of the study. This underscores why it is important to now position the current study in the context of corporate governance practices. This may help establish the linkage between corporate governance and public procurement and how it contributes towards curbing procurement breaches in the public sector.

The examination of the role of good corporate governance practices is important. This is because Osei-Tutu *et al.* (2010) recommended that the severity of corruption practices requires the search for more innovative means of delivering infrastructure projects that will achieve value for money. They (*ibid*) further argued that to control corruption practices, institutions would require a constitution that includes a sound procurement system and pro-social equity policies that would foster good governance, corporate social responsibility, transparency, accountability, judicious public expenditure and national progress. However, extensive research has not been conducted within the Ghanaian literature to establish how the elements of good governance (i.e., corporate social responsibility, transparency and accountability) contributes to curbing corruption practices in procurement for the delivery of infrastructure projects.

In other international research, Rotchanakitumnuai (2013) sought to present the factors of e-government procurement (E-GP) in Thailand that can create good governance in government procurement through e-auction. The study (*ibid*) found that there were five factors that enhance governance procurement, namely: 1) transparent e-procurement process; 2) committed public managers and political officials; 3) honest vendors; 4) specific policies and regulations; and 5) proficient and qualified practitioners. The results further indicated that a transparent e-procurement process has a positive effect on good governance practice, increasing cost effectiveness and accountability, and decreasing collusion among vendors. Vendor honesty has a negative impact on collusion (Hawkins *et al.*, 2014). Supportive regulations and policy requirements also improve cost effectiveness, accountability and law enforcement (Milligan *et al.*, 2017).

Jibrin *et al.* (2014) utilised published data on the extent of implementation and compliance with the Nigerian regulations. They (*ibid*) also looked at those of other developing and developed countries as a foundation for concluding that there has been a major improvement in public procurement law awareness, but that execution and compliance in the public sector are still lacking. The study identified media publicity; planning, organisational culture and political interference as factors that contribute both positively and negatively to public procurement implementation and compliance. While factors like media publicity and planning led to reduction in procurement breaches, organisational culture and political interference are identified as fuelling factors of procurement blunders (Damoah *et al.*, 2015). This underscores the need to identify the institutional factors which either reduce or promote effective implementation of procurement laws in Ghana. Importantly and akin to Osei-Tutu *et al.* (2010), Jibrin *et al.* (2014) did not include corporate governance and its influence in their study, a gap that is filled in this present study.

In Ethiopia, Ambaw and Telgen, (2017) assessed the extent of performance-based contracting (PBC) application and the obstacles to applying it in the public procurement systems of developing countries. The study's results (*ibid*) indicate that most public organizations have not yet used PBC even though it is allowed by the law. Contrasting the findings of Ambaw and Telgen (*ibid*) to that of Glas *et al.*, (2017) in Germany, it was identified that legislation ensures smooth implementation of procurement practices. However, in the case of Glas *et al.*, (*ibid*) the implementation strategy was different in centralized or state-level organizations compared with decentralized or local organizations. Centralized organizations give goals such as innovation, transparency and sustainability a high priority, while local ones highlight regional development and SME support.

The current study acknowledges the fact that various policies, regulations and laws about public procurement abounds in Ghana (Quashie, 2019). However, irrespective of which implementation strategy is adopted, researchers assert that institutional and behavioural factors either contribute positive or negatively to the implementation of these policies (Agyemang and Castellini, 2013; García-Sánchez, 2010). Additionally, within the public sector it is important to develop a comprehensive procurement framework capable of reducing or eliminating breaches to ensure efficient utilisation of public resources. Using data from Kenya, Nganu and Mwangangi (2019) sought to establish how procurement practices influence performance of state corporations. Sampling a total of 146 state corporations and using multiple regression analysis, the authors (*ibid*) proffered that good procurement practices enhance performance of state corporations. Specifically, the findings revealed that relationship management, strategic sourcing and adoption of information technology have significant influence on state corporations.

In Nigeria, Williams and Ehiabhi (2021) examined the extent to which the level of transparency influences public procurement practices in the Nigerian Civil Service. A survey research design was adopted for the study sampled 352 staff from all procurement department of all state institutions stationed in Nigeria's capital Abuja. Using simple

regression analysis, the results showed that public procurement practices are significantly and positively related to the level of transparency. In a related study Otera (2020) evaluated the impact of corporate governance on procurement compliance at Safaricom, Plc in Kenya. The study (*ibid*) reveals that corporate governance has a positive effect on procurement compliance with all the three variables (namely, accountability, corporate responsibility and transparency) indicating a positive effect. Although fairness had a positive effect on procurement compliance, it was not statistically significant. Therefore, the current study established the lagged relationship between corporate governance and public procurement and therefore, challenges the senior leadership of corporate entities to ensure that proper governance structures are instituted in their entities as they impact procurement compliance. The research implication was that procurement leadership should push for adoption of proper corporate governance because it leads to sustained productivity and better financial performance through procurement compliance.

Although Williams and Ehiabhi (2021) focused their attention on how transparency influence procurement, it could be argued that transparency is just a single aspect of good corporate governance practices (cf. Darko *et al.* 2016; Onyina, and Gyanor, 2019). This means that, to identify the real importance of corporate governance on public procurement, more elements or principles of corporate governance should be included. It is for this reason that the current study introduces other principles like accountability, fairness and board efficiency as key factors in public procurement.

6. Discussion

From the literature review, it is deduced that scant attention has been given to corporate governance and public procurement (Claessens and Yurtoglu). Other school of thoughts suggested that procurement cannot be taken as a separate activity from corporate governance (Solomon, 2020). However, considering the public sentiments on public procurement, it has become necessary to clearly define the function independently for the purpose of ensuring and promoting public confidence. It is also worth noting that there is limited literature to connect the two variables thus, corporate governance and public procurement and this may have a negative impact in the fight against corruption especially in the developing economies. Practically, an in-depth knowledge and understanding of the practices of corporate governance and public procurement would improve the judicious use of the limited resources especially in the public sector. The systematic review of the literature under the current study has established the shortfalls in the study of public procurement and therefore, practitioners and the academia are required to further research into the areas identified. Theoretically, the study has revealed that, procurement and corporate governance is integrated in human activities and therefore, is not static or rigid since it is bound to change under any circumstances. Therefore, pertinent theories (such as the Principal-Agent Theory, the Political Theory, Transaction Cost Theory, Stewardship) need to be critically examined when looking at the two variables because they would engender an holistic approach in public procurement activities for the purpose of ensuring value for money (Rein *et al.*, 2019).

Limitations and agenda for future research

This present study suggests that various thematic areas of future research investigation could be conducted by scholars in the field of corporate governance and procurement (more specifically, professionalism and transparency in public procurement and governance systems).

6.1. Professionalism and transparency in public procurement

Professionalism is the discipline whereby educated, experienced and responsible procurement officers make informed decisions regarding procurement functions (Naskar *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, it can be argued that the role that procurement professionals play in the procurement system of the Ghanaian economy is critical to Ghana's economic development (Public Procurement Board, 2007). Moreover, in recognition of this fact that one important object of the Public Procurement Board states: *"the professional development, promotion and support for individuals engaged in public procurement and to ensure adherence to ethical standards by trained persons."* Transparency, on the other hand, means the application of the same rules to all suppliers of goods, works and services and that these rules are publicized as the basis of procurement decisions before their use (Ruth *et al.*, 2021). Transparency enables the creation of open, fair and transparent procurement procedures and helps in the growth of in-country investments and competitiveness as the public sector is seen as a responsible business partner (Bandiyono *et al.*, 2020). Given the public sentiments and their quest for accountability from duty bearers in respect to public procurement and corporate governance, the current study suggest that future studies should public boards and management efficiencies. Another critical area to look at include corporate strategy, organisational budgeting and procurement planning.

7. Conclusion and recommendations

The study shows that although the principles of good governance vary across nations, accountability and transparency remain shared goals. Public procurement attempts to integrate these goals within practice yet, as demonstrated by the Ghana case, is impeded by shifting political landscapes, pressures to achieve competing objectives with limited resources and the need to satisfying diverse, and often conflicting, stakeholder expectations. This then raises the issue: at what level does the achievement of good governance give way to administrative and cost-efficiency goals? The study has discovered that public procurement professionals are keen to enhance public services and contribute towards social and economic reform – the work has also presented cases where they have succeeded. Yet, public procurement’s function as a pillar of good governance appears to remain popular rhetoric, as opposed to mainstream practice. The review recommends that, clear corporate governance guidelines and strategies should be linked to public procurement and how this can improve procurement performance. Again these strategies should be standardized across common public procurement entities and should be binding on duty holders.

It was identified that work has been done in the areas of corporate governance and public procurement remains scant particularly in Ghana. In addition, there was limited literature that dealt into these variables (viz. corporate governance practices and public procurement) especially in the developing economies and this is less to be desired for national development. Also, the findings also showed that, the thin line between corporate governance practices and public procurement practices should be clearly defined in order to promote independence of procurement practices in the sub region. It is very necessary for more education on best practices and the enactment of legal systems that can easily be integrated in our emerging markets.

Compliance with ethical standards

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I write on myself and by the permission of the underlisted co-authors to declare that there is not outstanding conflict in respect to this particular paper and all materials used to come with the paper was fully acknowledged.

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